

SCF(FBXW7)-mediated degradation of p53 promotes cell recovery after UV-induced DNA damage

María Galindo-Moreno^{1,†}, Servando Giráldez^{1,2,†}, M. Cristina Limón-Mortés¹,
Alejandro Belmonte-Fernández¹, Steven I. Reed², Carmen Sáez^{3,4}, Miguel Á. Japón^{3,4},
Maria Tortolero¹ and Francisco Romero^{1,*}

¹ Departamento de Microbiología, Facultad de Biología, Universidad de Sevilla, Sevilla, E-41012, Spain.

² Department of Molecular Medicine, The Scripps Research Institute, CA-92037, La Jolla, San Diego, USA.

³ Instituto de Biomedicina de Sevilla (IBiS), Hospital Universitario Virgen del Rocío/CSIC/Universidad de Sevilla, Sevilla, E-41013, Spain.

⁴ Departamento de Anatomía Patológica, Hospital Universitario Virgen del Rocío, Sevilla, E-41013, Spain.

† These authors contributed equally to this work.

* Corresponding author. Address: Departamento de Microbiología, Facultad de Biología, Avenida Reina Mercedes, 6. 41012-Sevilla, Spain. Tel: +34 954557119; E-mail: frport@us.es

Short title: Role of FBXW7 in cell recovery after DNA damage

ABBREVIATIONS

APC/C, anaphase-promoting complex/cyclosome; CHX, cycloheximide; CPD, CDC4-phosphodegron; DO-wl, yeast drop-out medium lacking Trp and Leu; DO-wlh, yeast drop-out medium lacking Trp, Leu, and His; E1, ubiquitin-activating enzyme; E2, ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme; E3, ubiquitin ligase; EGFP, enhanced green fluorescent protein; FBXW7, F-box and WD repeat domain containing 7; GSK3, glycogen synthase kinase 3; HA, hemagglutinin; NP40, Nonidet P-40; SCF, SKP1/CUL1/ F-box protein; siRNA, small interfering RNA; WT, wild type.

ABSTRACT

Eukaryotic cells have developed sophisticated mechanisms to ensure the integrity of the genome and prevent the transmission of altered genetic information to daughter cells. If this control system fails, accumulation of mutations would increase risk of diseases such as cancer. Ubiquitylation, an essential process for protein degradation and signal transduction, is critical for ensuring genome integrity, as well as almost all cellular functions. Here, we investigated the role of the SCF(FBXW7) ubiquitin ligase in cell proliferation by searching for targets implicated in this process. We identified a hitherto unknown FBXW7 interacting protein, p53, which is phosphorylated by glycogen synthase kinase 3 (GSK3) at serine 33 and then ubiquitylated by SCF(FBXW7) and degraded. This ubiquitylation is carried out both in normally growing cells, but primarily after DNA damage. Specifically, we found that SCF(FBXW7)-specific targeting of p53 is crucial for the recovery of cell proliferation after UV-induced DNA damage. Furthermore, we observed that amplification of FBXW7 in wild type p53 tumors reduced the survival of breast cancer patients. These results provide a rationale for using SCF(FBXW7) inhibitors in the treatment of this subset of tumors.

Key words: ubiquitylation, proliferation, cancer, FBXW7 inhibitors.

INTRODUCTION

Protein degradation plays an essential role in maintaining cellular homeostasis. For that reason, its deregulation is associated with many pathologies, including tumorigenesis. The ubiquitin system controls the stability of innumerable proteins that are degraded by the proteasome or lysosome (1). Ubiquitylation requires the concerted action of 3 enzymes, E1, E2 and E3. E3's, also known as ubiquitin ligases, are responsible for substrate recognition (2). The mammalian genome encodes approximately 1,000 E3 ubiquitin ligases. Among them, the anaphase-promoting complex/cyclosome (APC/C) and the SKP1/Cullin-1/F-box protein (SCF) complex are the two main ubiquitin ligases involved in cell cycle regulation (3). The F-box protein is the subunit of the SCF complex responsible for recruiting substrates. β TrCP, FBXW7 and SKP2 are the best-characterized of these.

In mammalian cells, there are three FBXW7 isoforms, FBXW7 α , FBXW7 β , and FBXW7 γ , which have distinct patterns of subcellular localization: FBXW7 α is nucleoplasmic, FBXW7 β is cytoplasmic, and FBXW7 γ is nucleolar (4). *FBXW7* is ubiquitously expressed (5) and targets multiple oncoproteins for proteolysis, such as cyclin E, c-JUN, c-MYC, MCL1, PLK1 or Notch (6). Therefore, it is considered an important tumor suppressor. In fact, *FBXW7* is one of the most commonly mutated genes in cancer. It is frequently mutated in T-cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia, colorectal adenocarcinoma, uterine carcinosarcoma and endometrial carcinoma, and bladder carcinoma; but also in stomach adenocarcinoma and lung, cervical and head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (7). Approximately 6% of 1,556 human cancers analyzed had inactivating mutations in *FBXW7* (8). FBXW7 recognizes phosphorylated motifs, known as CDC4-phosphodegrons (CPDs), within their substrates. The CPD consensus motif is (L)-X-pT/pS-P-(P)-X_{1,2}{X \neq K/R}-pT/pS/E/D, where X represents any amino acid (9-11). Frequently, glycogen synthase kinase 3 (GSK3) is responsible for phosphorylation of this motif, creating a FBXW7 binding site, thereby allowing ubiquitylation and degradation of substrates (12). In addition, FBXW7 dimerizes, which is especially important for those substrates with non-canonical phosphodegrons (13). We previously reported a search for new SCF(FBXW7) substrates by identifying FBXW7-interacting proteins using tandem mass spectrometry (14). We found that PLK1 is ubiquitylated and degraded by SCF(FBXW7) and the proteasome, respectively. Interestingly, we showed that after DNA damage in S phase, FBXW7-induced PLK1

degradation impedes the formation of pre-replication complexes, required for DNA replication (15), thus preventing cell proliferation. Our results suggested that the tumor suppressor function of FBXW7 might be related, at least in part, to its role in control of PLK1 levels.

In the current study, we continue our investigation of the role of FBXW7 in cell proliferation, specifically in the recovery from cell cycle arrest caused by DNA damage. We found that SCF(FBXW7) promotes cell proliferation by reducing protein levels of tumor suppressor p53 after DNA-damage-induced long-term arrest. SCF(FBXW7)-dependent degradation of p53 is mediated by GSK3 phosphorylation. We show that this decrease in p53 levels results in increased proliferation, as well as a reduction in cell death. Finally, we present evidence showing that FBXW7 status has potential consequences for cancer patients due to this regulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plasmids, cloning, point mutations and sequencing

pFlagCMV2-FBXW7, pCMVHA-FBXW7, pCMVHA-FBXW7 Δ F, pCS2HA- β TrCP, pRc/CMVhp53, pLexA-Ras^{V12}, pGAD-Raf and empty vectors have been previously described (14, 16-20). pEGFP-N1 and pCW7 (pRG4Myc-Ub) were from BD Biosciences (Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA) and ATCC (Manassas, VA, USA), respectively. pFlagCMV2-p53, pCMVHA-p53, pCMVHA-p53 S33G and the two-hybrid vectors pLex10-FBXW7 and pGAD-p53 were obtained by cloning the corresponding PCR fragments in pFlagCMV2, pCMVHA, pLex10, and pGAD-GH, respectively. p53 S33G, p53 S46A, p53 T81A, p53 S149A/T150A and p53 L14Q/F19G were constructed using the Q5[®] Site-Directed Mutagenesis Kit from New England Biolabs Inc (Ipswich, MA, USA). The sequences of constructs and point mutations were verified on both strands with an automatic sequencer.

Yeast two-hybrid methods

Saccharomyces cerevisiae strain L40 was co-transformed with the indicated plasmids by the lithium acetate method (20). Double transformants were plated on yeast drop-out medium lacking Trp and Leu (DO-wl). They were grown for 3 days at 30°C, and then colonies were patched on the same medium and replica-plated on Whatman 40 filters to test for β -galactosidase activity (21), and on yeast drop-out medium lacking Trp, Leu,

and His (DO-wlh). Plasmids pLexA-Ras^{V12} and pGAD-Raf carrying proteins that interact with each other, were used as controls (20).

Cell culture, transient transfections, drugs and cell lysis

Routinely, Cos7, U2OS and HEK293T (from ATCC) were grown in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (BioWest, Nuaille, France) as described (22). HCT116, HCT116^{FBXW7^{-/-}}, DLD1 and DLD1^{FBXW7^{-/-}} (23), and HCT116^{p53^{-/-}} (24) were grown in McCoy's 5A medium (BioWest) supplemented with 10% (v/v) fetal bovine serum, 100 µg/ml streptomycin and 100 U/ml penicillin from Gibco (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). DNA constructs were transiently transfected by electroporation or by using a lipid transfection reagent (Xfect, Clontech, Mountain View, CA, USA). Cells were harvested and lysed 18h or 48h post-transfection, respectively. Where appropriate, transfected cells were re-transfected with other plasmids. In indicated experiments, cells or extracts were pretreated with cycloheximide (CHX 50 µg/ml, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA), Nutlin 3a (20 µM, Sigma-Aldrich), LiCl (100 mM, Sigma-Aldrich), CHIR99021 (10 µM, Sigma-Aldrich) or GSK3β inhibitor VII (100-200 µM, Calbiochem, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), and harvested at various times.

Whole cell extracts were prepared at 4° C in 420 mM NaCl, 10 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.5), 1% Nonidet P-40 (NP40), 10% glycerol, 1 mM phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (PMSF), 1 µg/ml aprotinin, 1 µg/ml pepstatin, 1 µg/ml leupeptin and 10 µg/ml chymostatin for 20 min. Extracts were centrifuged at 20,000g for 20 min and supernatants frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80° C. Protein concentration was determined using the Bradford assay (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA).

Knock down experiments

Cells were transfected with FBXW7α- or GSK3α/β-siRNA (25-27) using the Oligofectamine method (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) to suppress the expression of endogenous genes. EGFP-siRNA (25) was used as a non-specific control. Cells were harvested 48 h post-transfection and the reduction of protein levels confirmed by Western blotting.

Electrophoresis, Western blot analysis and antibodies

Proteins were separated by SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) and gels were electroblotted onto nitrocellulose membranes and probed with the following antibodies: anti-HA-peroxidase monoclonal antibody (Roche, Basel Switzerland); anti-cyclin E, anti-MDM2, anti-p53 and anti-GSK3 α/β monoclonal antibodies (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Dallas, TX, USA); anti- α -Tubulin and anti-Flag monoclonal antibodies (Sigma-Aldrich); anti-GFP polyclonal antibody (Immune Systems Ltd., Paignton, UK); anti-GSK3 β and anti-PARP monoclonal antibodies (BD Biosciences); anti-PLK1 monoclonal antibody (EMD Millipore, Merck); anti-p-p53 (Ser33) monoclonal antibody (Abcam, Cambridge, UK), and anti-p-GSK3 β (Ser9) and anti-cleaved caspase-3 monoclonal antibodies (Cell Signaling Technology, Danvers, MA, USA). Peroxidase-coupled donkey anti-rabbit IgG and sheep anti-mouse IgG were obtained from GE Healthcare (Little Chalfont, UK). Immunoreactive bands were visualized using the Enhanced Chemiluminescence Western blotting system (ECL, GE Healthcare).

Co-immunoprecipitation experiments

Whole cell extracts from transfected cells diluted to 150 mM NaCl (1-2 mg) were incubated with normal mouse serum (Santa Cruz Biotechnology) for 30 minutes and subsequently with protein G-sepharose beads (GE Healthcare) for 1 hour at 4° C. After centrifugation, the beads were discarded and the supernatants incubated for 2 hours with anti-p53 (Santa Cruz Biotechnology) or anti-Flag (Sigma-Aldrich) mouse monoclonal antibodies followed by protein G-sepharose beads for 1 hour. Alternatively, the supernatants were incubated with normal mouse serum. Beads were washed and bound proteins were solubilized by the addition of SDS-sample buffer heated at 95° C for 5 minutes.

***In vitro* and *in vivo* ubiquitylation assays**

The *in vitro* ubiquitylation of p53 was performed in a volume of 10 μ l containing 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.6), 5 mM MgCl₂, 0.6 mM DTT, 2 mM ATP, 2 μ l *in vitro* transcribed/translated unlabeled F-box protein, 1.5 ng/ μ l E1 (His₆-ubiquitin activating enzyme, Boston Biochem, Cambridge, MA, USA), 10 ng/ μ l His₆-UbcH3 (E2, Boston Biochem), 10 ng/ μ l UbcH5a (E2, Boston Biochem), 2.5 μ g/ μ l ubiquitin (Sigma-Aldrich), 1 μ M ubiquitin aldehyde (Boston Biochem), and 1 μ l ³⁵S-methionine-labelled *in vitro* transcribed/translated p53 as substrate. The reactions were incubated at 30° C

for 1 hour and analyzed by SDS-PAGE and autoradiography. For some experiments the unlabeled F-box protein was substituted by a recombinant SCF(FBXW7) complex expressed in Sf21 insect cells.

The *in vivo* ubiquitylation experiments were performed in Cos7 cells transfected and treated with MG132 4 hours before harvesting. Cells were washed in PBS, lysed at 95° C for 15 minutes in NP40 buffer (28) supplemented with 5% SDS and 10 mM iodoacetamide, and diluted in NP40 buffer supplemented with 10 mM iodoacetamide. Flag-p53 was immunoprecipitated and proteins were separated by SDS-PAGE, electroblotted and probed with different antibodies.

***In vitro* kinase assay**

In vitro transcribed/translated HA-p53 and HA-p53 S33G were incubated in the presence or absence of human recombinant GSK3 β (Invitrogen) with ATP 200 μ M and GSK3 β buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.5), 10 mM MgCl₂, 100 μ M Na₃VO₄ and 2 mM DTT) for 30 min at 30 °C. For some experiments, GSK3 β inhibitor VII was previously added. Reactions were terminated by adding SDS-sample buffer, and proteins analyzed by Western blot.

Cell proliferation assay

Cells were cultured in 6 cm dishes at 5×10^5 cells/plate with the appropriate medium to ensure exponential growth for duration of the assay. After 24h, cells were UV irradiated (60J/m², 254 nm) and harvested at the indicated times. The amount of proteins in the extracts, quantified by the Bradford assay, was taken as a parameter to measure cell proliferation. Experiments were performed independently at least three times.

Crystal violet assay

Briefly, transfected cells were seeded in 6-well plates and, after 24h, irradiated. At the indicated times cells were stained with 0.5% crystal violet solution in methanol for 20 min. After washing and air-drying, stained cells were incubated with methanol for 20 min and absorbance at 570 nm measured with a plate reader. All assays were carried out in triplicate.

Patient dataset collection

Patients' clinical data and copy number alterations of genes were downloaded from cBioPortal database (TCGA and METABRIC for breast invasive carcinoma and breast cancer, respectively, TCGA and MSKCC for bladder cancer, and TCGA for skin cutaneous melanoma) (29, 30), and are freely available. Survival curves were generated using the Kaplan-Meier method.

Quantification and statistical analysis

Statistical details of experiments (number of biological replicates and use of standard deviation) are included in the Figure Legends. Statistical analyses were done with unpaired Student's *t*-tests. Significance is indicated in figures as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ and *** $p < 0.001$.

Survival curves were calculated by the method of Kaplan and Meier. The comparison of the survival curves was done by the log-rank test of Mantel and Cox. Differences were considered significant when $p < 0.05$. Calculations were performed using Prism 6.0 (GraphPad, San Diego, CA, USA).

RESULTS

p53 is a substrate for SCF(FBXW7) ubiquitin ligase

To find new SCF(FBXW7) substrates, we previously immunoprecipitated epitope-tagged FBXW7 and identified co-precipitating proteins using mass spectrometry (14). Among the peptides identified, three were unique peptides corresponding to p53 not present in control samples from non-immune IgG immunoprecipitation (Fig. 1A). To verify the FBXW7/p53 interaction, we confirmed the presence of p53 within Flag-FBXW7 immunocomplexes by Western blot assay (Fig. 1B). Moreover, reciprocal co-immunoprecipitation analysis showed that Flag-FBXW7 also co-precipitated with endogenous p53 (Fig. 1C). Next, we cloned full-length human *FBXW7* and *TP53* cDNAs into two-hybrid vectors to analyze this interaction in yeast, where indirect association is less likely (31). Growth in the absence of histidine and expression of β -galactosidase activity indicated that FBXW7 interacts directly with p53 (Fig. 1D). Finally, we studied the ubiquitin ligase activity of SCF(FBXW7) on p53 both *in vitro*, using reticulocyte extracts (Fig. 1E) or proteins produced in Sf21 insect cells (Fig. 1F), and *in vivo* (Fig. 1G). In all three cases, p53 was specifically ubiquitylated by SCF(FBXW7). Therefore, our data show that p53 is a substrate of SCF(FBXW7).

FBXW7 contributes to the regulation of p53 turnover in unstressed mammalian cells

In order to test whether SCF(FBXW7) regulates p53 stability, we first assessed p53 levels in the absence of FBXW7 protein, either by using an *FBXW7*^{-/-} cell line (HCT116^{*FBXW7*^{-/-}}) (23) or through RNAi-mediated silencing experiments in HCT116 wild type cells. In both cases, we observed an increase of p53 protein level that was similar to that obtained with cyclin E, a known FBXW7 substrate used as a control (32), in the FBXW7-siRNA transfected cells (Fig. 2A). Consistent with this, the half-life of endogenous p53 in FBXW7-silenced cells was longer than in cells transfected with control siRNA targeting EGFP (Fig. 2B). Conversely, overexpression of FBXW7 in Cos7 cells induced a decrease in p53 protein. Figure 2C shows that FBXW7 overexpression caused a reduction of p53 levels that did not occur with overexpression of FBXW7 Δ F, a dominant-negative form of FBXW7 lacking the F-box domain, which couples F-box protein to the SCF complex (33). Next, we analyzed the p53 protein sequence to identify potential FBXW7 binding sites. We found 4 possible CPDs, as defined by a serine or threonine followed by a proline, at positions 33, 46, 81, and 149/150 (Fig. 2D, upper panel). To ascertain whether any of these motifs is a functional CPD, we mutated the indicated residues to alanine or glycine, and examined the degradation of these mutants by FBXW7 overexpression. Figure 2D (bottom panel) shows that only the mutation at Ser33 abrogated FBXW7-dependent p53 degradation. Therefore, FBXW7 is involved in p53 degradation in unstressed cells via an amino-terminal CPD including Ser33.

MDM2 is probably the most significant ubiquitin ligase responsible for p53 degradation under conditions where p53 is otherwise stabilized (34). To rule out that FBXW7 acts through MDM2 to regulate p53 levels, we followed two independent approaches. On the one hand, we evaluated the effect of Nutlin 3a, a small-molecule inhibitor of MDM2, on the level of p53 in wild type and *FBXW7*^{-/-} cells. We observed that, although the p53 levels increased significantly after Nutlin 3a treatment, there was still more p53 protein in *FBXW7*^{-/-} than in the wild type cells (Fig. 2E). On the other hand, we constructed a p53 mutant unable to bind to MDM2 (35), and tested whether its levels could be reduced by the overexpression of FBXW7. Figure 2F shows that the p53 mutant can still be degraded by SCF(FBXW7). These data, together with those obtained

in yeast showing a direct interaction between FBXW7 and p53, indicate that FBXW7 has a role in the degradation of p53 independently of MDM2.

SCF(FBXW7) plays a critical role in the recovery of cell proliferation after DNA damage

A number of ubiquitin ligases have a role in p53 degradation after DNA damage (36-38). To determine whether FBXW7 is also involved in this process, we compared the increase of p53 protein levels after UV irradiation in both HCT116 and HCT116^{FBXW7-/-} cell lines. We found that the presence of FBXW7 did not reduce p53 levels, at least within 24h after DNA damage (Supplemental Fig. S1).

Next, we studied p53 stability and cell proliferation in the long-term after UV irradiation in wild type and FBXW7-deficient cells. We detected an increase of cell proliferation 3 days after UV irradiation in HCT116 cells (Fig. 3A) matching with a decrease of p53 protein (Fig. 3B, C). However, cells lacking FBXW7 began to proliferate 7 days after irradiation, consistent with persistence of high levels of p53 protein. Similar experiments were performed using DLD1 and DLD1^{FBXW7-/-} cell lines, a cell model that is negative for functional p53 protein, unlike the HCT116 model (39). Using the DLD1 cell model, we did not observe proliferation differences after UV in the presence or absence of FBXW7. However, p53 was degraded in an FBXW7-dependent manner in this cell line (Supplemental Fig. S2). Together, these results indicate that FBXW7 is required for the recovery of cell proliferation after DNA damage, and suggest specifically that the degradation of a functional p53 by SCF(FBXW7) is required for this process.

Therefore, we can conclude that FBXW7 controls long-term p53 levels after DNA damage promoting cell proliferation.

Phosphorylation of p53 by GSK3 triggers its degradation by SCF(FBXW7)

GSK3 β is a major kinase involved in the phosphorylation of SCF(FBXW7) substrates (12). In addition, it has been previously reported that GSK3 β phosphorylates Ser33 of p53 (40). Therefore, we sought to determine whether GSK3 was responsible for the degradation of p53 by SCF(FBXW7). We first verified that GSK3 β phosphorylates p53 Ser33 *in vitro*. Using a coupled *in vitro* transcription and translation system and a specific anti-phospho-p53 (Ser33) antibody, we observed that GSK3 β phosphorylated

p53 at Ser33 and that this phosphorylation was prevented by a GSK3 β inhibitor (Fig. 4A). Then, we compared phospho-Ser33 levels in wild type and FBXW7-deficient cells. We found that the absence of FBXW7 allowed detection of Ser33 phosphorylation, especially in DLD1 cells (Fig. 4B). To ascertain whether this p53 phosphorylation was mediated by GSK3, we employed GSK3 inhibitors and silencing experiments (Fig. 4C, D), confirming that GSK3 is largely responsible for the phosphorylation of p53 Ser33 under basal conditions. Lastly, we overexpressed HA-FBXW7 in DLD1^{FBXW7^{-/-}} cells, which led to a decrease in phospho-Ser33 levels (Fig. 4E). Together, these data show that GSK3 triggers p53 degradation by SCF(FBXW7) in normally growing cells. Next, we wondered whether GSK3 was also involved in the degradation of p53 during the recovery of cell proliferation. We therefore compared the phosphorylation level of Ser33 after UV irradiation in DLD1 and DLD1^{FBXW7^{-/-}} cells. We observed that the phospho-Ser33 level remained constant after UV irradiation in cells lacking FBXW7, while it decreased in wild type cells (Fig. 4F). These results suggest that p53 must be phosphorylated by GSK3 after UV to be degraded by SCF(FBXW7). Furthermore, the inhibition of GSK3 enzymatic activity after irradiation reduced Ser33 phosphorylation (Fig. 4G), implicating this kinase in the recovery of cell proliferation. Therefore, our results strongly support a role for GSK3-dependent phosphorylation of serine 33 in p53 degradation by SCF(FBXW7) both under basal conditions and in the recovery of cell proliferation after DNA damage.

Involvement of FBXW7 on cell proliferation recovery after UV is mediated by p53 degradation

To validate the direct involvement of p53 degradation by SCF(FBXW7) in the recovery of cell proliferation after UV damage, we transfected HCT116^{p53^{-/-}} cells with p53 or p53 S33G, the mutated form of p53 resistant to degradation by SCF(FBXW7). We compared the ability of these lines to proliferate after UV irradiation by using a clonal survival assay for determining cell viability. As a control we used HCT116^{FBXW7^{-/-}} cells transfected with empty vector. Figure 5A shows that while HCT116^{p53^{-/-}} (pFlagCMV2p53) formed colonies few days after being irradiated, HCT116^{p53^{-/-}} (pFlagCMV2p53 S33G) and HCT116^{FBXW7^{-/-}} (pFlagCMV2) did not. Thus, cells lacking FBXW7 behave the similarly to those expressing p53 that is resistant to degradation by SCF(FBXW7) (Fig. 5B). These results show that the role carried out by FBXW7 in the recovery of cell proliferation after DNA damage is mediated by the degradation of p53.

FBXW7 reduces UV-induced p53-dependent cell death

To further evaluate the pivotal role of FBXW7 in recovery of proliferation after DNA-damage, we assessed the level of apoptosis induced by UV irradiation in cells lacking FBXW7 versus wild type HCT116 cells. We observed a lower level of cleaved PARP and activated caspase 3 at 48 hours after UV irradiation in HCT116 cells compared to HCT116^{FBXW7^{-/-}} cells (Fig. 6A, left panels), suggesting that the presence of FBXW7 also confers a reduction of UV-induced apoptosis in the HCT116 cell line. Again, similar experiments performed using the DLD1 cell model, in which apoptosis is p53-independent (41), did not show apparent differences between the wild type or *FBXW7^{-/-}* cells (Fig. 6A, right panels). Therefore, we conclude that FBXW7 accelerates the recovery of cell proliferation by also reducing p53-mediated apoptosis after damage. Finally, in order to assess the clinical implications of our findings, we analyzed the survival of cancer patients depending on their FBXW7 and p53 status. As FBXW7 is a well-documented tumor suppressor that is mutated or deleted in many tumors (most of them also mutated in p53), we wanted to explore the effect of an increase of FBXW7 (FBXW7^{amp}) on survival of patients with wild-type p53 tumors. Using data from the cBioPortal database (from The Cancer Genome Atlas, TCGA, and the Molecular Taxonomy of Breast Cancer International Consortium, METABRIC) (29, 30), we compared the survival of p53^{wt}/FBXW7^{amp} breast cancer patients (n=68) versus p53^{wt}/FBXW7^{wt} patients (n=1,453). Interestingly, we found poorer survival in patients who had tumors with amplified FBXW7 versus those who did not (p=0.001) (Fig. 6B). Conversely, the increase of FBXW7 did not significantly alter the survival of patients suffering breast cancer carrying p53 mutations (p53^{loss}/FBXW7^{amp}, n=73 versus p53^{loss}/FBXW7^{wt}, n=852) (Fig. 6C), suggesting that the role of FBXW7 in breast cancer patient survival occurs through p53. Despite the above, the survival analysis of bladder cancer or skin cutaneous melanoma patients who had tumors with FBXW7^{amp} did not show significant differences in survival relative to those who did not (data not shown). The low number of patients under analysis (19 and 29 patients, respectively) may account for the lack of a significant correlation. Nevertheless, taken together, our results lead us to suggest that depending on a patient's genetic profile, FBXW7 inhibition might be a reasonable therapeutic approach.

DISCUSSION

The *TP53* tumor suppressor gene is the most frequently mutated gene in human cancer. In fact, it has been reported that at least 50% of human malignancies contain *TP53* mutations, being especially predominant in carcinomas of ovary and endometrium, and in basal subtype breast tumors (42). This high frequency of mutation is consistent with its role in cell cycle regulation, senescence and apoptosis. p53 activates transcription of many genes, including those that encode proteins involved in cell cycle arrest, such as p21^{WAF1/CIP1}, or pro-apoptotic proteins, such as PUMA, NOXA or FAS (43, 44). In unstressed cells, the p53 protein level is low due to proteasomal degradation mainly mediated by MDM2 (34), although other ubiquitin ligases may also be involved (45). However, in response to many stress signals such as DNA damage, aberrant oncogenic signaling, nutrient deprivation or hypoxia, p53 accumulates in the nucleus and transactivates numerous target genes. Depending on the stress intensity, cells can resume proliferation after repairing the damage or die by apoptosis or necroptosis if the damage is irreparable. To successfully recover from the arrest, p53 must be inactivated. As p53 activation is largely mediated by phosphorylation, several phosphatases have been described that are likely to be involved in p53 inactivation: WIP1, which dephosphorylates p53 at serine 15 reversing the G2/M cell cycle arrest caused by DNA damage (46); DUSP26, which inhibits the p53 tumor suppressor function dephosphorylating serines 20 and 37 (47); PP1, which also dephosphorylates serine 15 of p53 and stabilizes the p53 regulator MDMX (48); and PP4, among others, which reverses the p53-mediated G1 arrest induced by DNA damage (49). These phosphatases dephosphorylate p53, thereby affecting its stability, and/or its regulators or effectors. In this study, we identify a new mechanism involved in the release from p53 checkpoint arrest after UV irradiation. We found that FBXW7 is needed to support recovery of proliferation once DNA damage has been repaired. GSK3 phosphorylates p53 at serine 33 triggering its ubiquitylation and degradation by SCF(FBXW7). This reduction in p53 levels allows the recovery of cell proliferation. Interestingly, *FBXW7* has been described as a p53 transcriptional target gene (50, 51), suggesting that FBXW7 likely operates as part of a negative feedback regulatory loop with p53. Thus, the stress induced accumulation and activation of p53 up-regulates FBXW7, which in turn leads to ubiquitylation and degradation of p53 once the stress has been removed. Since our results show that FBXW7 enhances proliferation under certain conditions, we analyzed survival of p53^{wt}/FBXW7^{amp} cancer patients using cBioPortal database. In this context, we found that increased FBXW7 reduced the survival of breast cancer patients.

Therefore, it may be reasonable to propose the use of FBXW7 inhibitors for the treatment of this subset of tumors. One could envision a treatment based on DNA damaging agents to induce p53, and inhibitors of FBXW7 to prevent its degradation. In that way, perhaps p53-mediated apoptosis would promote tumor regression. Another situation in which it may be convenient to inhibit FBXW7 is in the maintenance of quiescence in the leukemia-initiating cells (LICs) of chronic myeloid leukemia (CML). Ablation of *FBXW7* increased sensitivity of LICs to imatinib, an anticancer drug that targets dividing cells. Thus, combination of FBXW7 inhibitors and imatinib may provide a promising therapeutic approach to CML (52). Therefore, it seems increasingly clear that the classic distinction between oncogenes and tumor suppressors is dependent on cellular context. Thus, a tumor suppressor can promote tumorigenesis when mutated or deleted, but perhaps also reduce survival when overexpressed. In agreement with this idea, other F-box proteins, such as β TrCP, can also act as an oncoprotein or a tumor-suppressor protein in a cellular context-dependent manner, in this case mainly due to the diversity of substrates (53).

In the present work, we leave open an additional question that would be interesting to address in future studies. We have elucidated that once cells repair the damage induced by UV irradiation, SCF(FBXW7) degrades p53. However, immediately after the damage occurs, the presence of FBXW7 allows a rapid accumulation of p53. A plausible explanation would be that FBXW7 contributes to the degradation of a negative p53 regulator in response to DNA damage, although currently we have no evidence supporting this hypothesis.

Taking together, our findings provide evidence for a new mechanism of regulation of the p53-mediated DNA damage response through FBXW7. Specifically, we show that after DNA damage FBXW7 contributes to arrest the cell cycle allowing a rapid increase of p53, and when damage has been repaired, FBXW7-mediated degradation of p53 allows recovery of cell proliferation. Given the crucial role of FBXW7 in cell proliferation, but also in growth, and differentiation, and its pivotal role in tumorigenesis, it is essential to know the context-dependent function of this protein. Such an endeavor could pave the way for development of personalized therapies, including treatments based on FBXW7 inhibitors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by Spanish grants from Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness, MINECO (SAF2014-53799 and SAF2017-87358) and Junta de Andalucía (2017/BIO-211), and NIH grants CA078343 and GM115170 to S.I.R. A.B-F is the recipient of a Ph.D. fellowship from the VI PPI of University of Seville.

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

M.G.-M. and S.G. performed the main experiments and analyzed data; C.L.-M. and A.B.-F. designed and contributed to perform proliferation experiments; S.I.R. conceived and mentored some experiments; C.S. and M.A.J. performed cell cycle and Kaplan-Meier analysis and contributed to the discussion of the results; and M.T. and F.R. designed the research and wrote the manuscript with input from all other authors.

REFERENCES

1. Ji, C. H., and Kwon, Y. T. (2017) Crosstalk and Interplay between the Ubiquitin-Proteasome System and Autophagy. *Molecules and cells* **40**, 441-449
2. Kaiser, P., and Huang, L. (2005) Global approaches to understanding ubiquitination. *Genome biology* **6**, 233
3. Nakayama, K. I., and Nakayama, K. (2006) Ubiquitin ligases: cell-cycle control and cancer. *Nature reviews. Cancer* **6**, 369-381
4. Welcker, M., Orian, A., Grim, J. E., Eisenman, R. N., and Clurman, B. E. (2004) A nucleolar isoform of the Fbw7 ubiquitin ligase regulates c-Myc and cell size. *Current biology : CB* **14**, 1852-1857
5. Grim, J. E., Gustafson, M. P., Hirata, R. K., Hagar, A. C., Swanger, J., Welcker, M., Hwang, H. C., Ericsson, J., Russell, D. W., and Clurman, B. E. (2008) Isoform- and cell cycle-dependent substrate degradation by the Fbw7 ubiquitin ligase. *The Journal of cell biology* **181**, 913-920
6. Heo, J., Eki, R., and Abbas, T. (2016) Deregulation of F-box proteins and its consequence on cancer development, progression and metastasis. *Seminars in cancer biology* **36**, 33-51
7. Davis, R. J., Welcker, M., and Clurman, B. E. (2014) Tumor suppression by the Fbw7 ubiquitin ligase: mechanisms and opportunities. *Cancer cell* **26**, 455-464

8. Akhoondi, S., Sun, D., von der Lehr, N., Apostolidou, S., Klotz, K., Maljukova, A., Cepeda, D., Fiegl, H., Dafou, D., Marth, C., Mueller-Holzner, E., Corcoran, M., Dagnell, M., Nejad, S. Z., Nayer, B. N., Zali, M. R., Hansson, J., Egyhazi, S., Petersson, F., Sangfelt, P., Nordgren, H., Grander, D., Reed, S. I., Widschwendter, M., Sangfelt, O., and Spruck, C. (2007) FBXW7/hCDC4 is a general tumor suppressor in human cancer. *Cancer research* **67**, 9006-9012
9. Nash, P., Tang, X., Orlicky, S., Chen, Q., Gertler, F. B., Mendenhall, M. D., Sicheri, F., Pawson, T., and Tyers, M. (2001) Multisite phosphorylation of a CDK inhibitor sets a threshold for the onset of DNA replication. *Nature* **414**, 514-521
10. Orlicky, S., Tang, X., Willems, A., Tyers, M., and Sicheri, F. (2003) Structural basis for phosphodependent substrate selection and orientation by the SCFCdc4 ubiquitin ligase. *Cell* **112**, 243-256
11. Tang, X., Orlicky, S., Liu, Q., Willems, A., Sicheri, F., and Tyers, M. (2005) Genome-wide surveys for phosphorylation-dependent substrates of SCF ubiquitin ligases. *Methods in enzymology* **399**, 433-458
12. Welcker, M., and Clurman, B. E. (2008) FBW7 ubiquitin ligase: a tumour suppressor at the crossroads of cell division, growth and differentiation. *Nature reviews. Cancer* **8**, 83-93
13. Welcker, M., Larimore, E. A., Swanger, J., Bengoechea-Alonso, M. T., Grim, J. E., Ericsson, J., Zheng, N., and Clurman, B. E. (2013) Fbw7 dimerization determines the specificity and robustness of substrate degradation. *Genes & development* **27**, 2531-2536
14. Giraldez, S., Herrero-Ruiz, J., Mora-Santos, M., Japon, M. A., Tortolero, M., and Romero, F. (2014) SCF(FBXW7 α) modulates the intra-S-phase DNA-damage checkpoint by regulating Polo like kinase-1 stability. *Oncotarget* **5**, 4370-4383
15. Leman, A. R., and Noguchi, E. (2013) The replication fork: understanding the eukaryotic replication machinery and the challenges to genome duplication. *Genes* **4**, 1-32
16. Chen, J., Wu, X., Lin, J., and Levine, A. J. (1996) mdm-2 inhibits the G1 arrest and apoptosis functions of the p53 tumor suppressor protein. *Molecular and cellular biology* **16**, 2445-2452

17. Fukuda, T., Naiki, T., Saito, M., and Irie, K. (2009) hnRNP K interacts with RNA binding motif protein 42 and functions in the maintenance of cellular ATP level during stress conditions. *Genes to cells : devoted to molecular & cellular mechanisms* **14**, 113-128
18. Klotz, K., Cepeda, D., Tan, Y., Sun, D., Sangfelt, O., and Spruck, C. (2009) SCF(Fbxw7/hCdc4) targets cyclin E2 for ubiquitin-dependent proteolysis. *Experimental cell research* **315**, 1832-1839
19. Margottin, F., Bour, S. P., Durand, H., Selig, L., Benichou, S., Richard, V., Thomas, D., Strebel, K., and Benarous, R. (1998) A novel human WD protein, h-beta TrCp, that interacts with HIV-1 Vpu connects CD4 to the ER degradation pathway through an F-box motif. *Mol Cell* **1**, 565-574
20. Romero, F., Dargemont, C., Pozo, F., Reeves, W. H., Camonis, J., Gisselbrecht, S., and Fischer, S. (1996) p95vav associates with the nuclear protein Ku-70. *Molecular and cellular biology* **16**, 37-44
21. Breeden, L., and Nasmyth, K. (1985) Regulation of the yeast HO gene. *Cold Spring Harbor symposia on quantitative biology* **50**, 643-650
22. Romero, F., Gil-Bernabe, A. M., Saez, C., Japon, M. A., Pintor-Toro, J. A., and Tortolero, M. (2004) Securin is a target of the UV response pathway in mammalian cells. *Molecular and cellular biology* **24**, 2720-2733
23. Rajagopalan, H., Jallepalli, P. V., Rago, C., Velculescu, V. E., Kinzler, K. W., Vogelstein, B., and Lengauer, C. (2004) Inactivation of hCDC4 can cause chromosomal instability. *Nature* **428**, 77-81
24. Bunz, F., Hwang, P. M., Torraine, C., Waldman, T., Zhang, Y., Dillehay, L., Williams, J., Lengauer, C., Kinzler, K. W., and Vogelstein, B. (1999) Disruption of p53 in human cancer cells alters the responses to therapeutic agents. *The Journal of clinical investigation* **104**, 263-269
25. Lee, J. Y., Yu, S. J., Park, Y. G., Kim, J., and Sohn, J. (2007) Glycogen synthase kinase 3beta phosphorylates p21WAF1/CIP1 for proteasomal degradation after UV irradiation. *Molecular and cellular biology* **27**, 3187-3198
26. Phiel, C. J., Wilson, C. A., Lee, V. M., and Klein, P. S. (2003) GSK-3alpha regulates production of Alzheimer's disease amyloid-beta peptides. *Nature* **423**, 435-439
27. van Drogen, F., Sangfelt, O., Malyukova, A., Matskova, L., Yeh, E., Means, A. R., and Reed, S. I. (2006) Ubiquitylation of cyclin E requires the sequential

- function of SCF complexes containing distinct hCdc4 isoforms. *Mol Cell* **23**, 37-48
28. Romero, F., Multon, M. C., Ramos-Morales, F., Dominguez, A., Bernal, J. A., Pintor-Toro, J. A., and Tortolero, M. (2001) Human securin, hPTTG, is associated with Ku heterodimer, the regulatory subunit of the DNA-dependent protein kinase. *Nucleic acids research* **29**, 1300-1307
 29. Cerami, E., Gao, J., Dogrusoz, U., Gross, B. E., Sumer, S. O., Aksoy, B. A., Jacobsen, A., Byrne, C. J., Heuer, M. L., Larsson, E., Antipin, Y., Reva, B., Goldberg, A. P., Sander, C., and Schultz, N. (2012) The cBio cancer genomics portal: an open platform for exploring multidimensional cancer genomics data. *Cancer discovery* **2**, 401-404
 30. Gao, J., Aksoy, B. A., Dogrusoz, U., Dresdner, G., Gross, B., Sumer, S. O., Sun, Y., Jacobsen, A., Sinha, R., Larsson, E., Cerami, E., Sander, C., and Schultz, N. (2013) Integrative analysis of complex cancer genomics and clinical profiles using the cBioPortal. *Science signaling* **6**, p11
 31. Fields, S., and Song, O. (1989) A novel genetic system to detect protein-protein interactions. *Nature* **340**, 245-246
 32. Strohmaier, H., Spruck, C. H., Kaiser, P., Won, K. A., Sangfelt, O., and Reed, S. I. (2001) Human F-box protein hCdc4 targets cyclin E for proteolysis and is mutated in a breast cancer cell line. *Nature* **413**, 316-322
 33. Welcker, M., Orian, A., Jin, J., Grim, J. E., Harper, J. W., Eisenman, R. N., and Clurman, B. E. (2004) The Fbw7 tumor suppressor regulates glycogen synthase kinase 3 phosphorylation-dependent c-Myc protein degradation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **101**, 9085-9090
 34. Haupt, Y., Maya, R., Kazaz, A., and Oren, M. (1997) Mdm2 promotes the rapid degradation of p53. *Nature* **387**, 296-299
 35. Lin, J., Chen, J., Elenbaas, B., and Levine, A. J. (1994) Several hydrophobic amino acids in the p53 amino-terminal domain are required for transcriptional activation, binding to mdm-2 and the adenovirus 5 E1B 55-kD protein. *Genes & development* **8**, 1235-1246
 36. Hakem, A., Bohgaki, M., Lemmers, B., Tai, E., Salmena, L., Matysiak-Zablocki, E., Jung, Y. S., Karaskova, J., Kaustov, L., Duan, S., Madore, J., Boutros, P., Sheng, Y., Chesi, M., Bergsagel, P. L., Perez-Ordóñez, B., Mes-

- Masson, A. M., Penn, L., Squire, J., Chen, X., Jurisica, I., Arrowsmith, C., Sanchez, O., Benchimol, S., and Hakem, R. (2011) Role of Pirh2 in mediating the regulation of p53 and c-Myc. *PLoS genetics* **7**, e1002360
37. Xia, Y., Padre, R. C., De Mendoza, T. H., Bottero, V., Tergaonkar, V. B., and Verma, I. M. (2009) Phosphorylation of p53 by IkappaB kinase 2 promotes its degradation by beta-TrCP. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **106**, 2629-2634
38. Yang, W., Rozan, L. M., McDonald, E. R., 3rd, Navaraj, A., Liu, J. J., Matthew, E. M., Wang, W., Dicker, D. T., and El-Deiry, W. S. (2007) CARPs are ubiquitin ligases that promote MDM2-independent p53 and phospho-p53ser20 degradation. *The Journal of biological chemistry* **282**, 3273-3281
39. O'Connor, P. M., Jackman, J., Bae, I., Myers, T. G., Fan, S., Mutoh, M., Scudiero, D. A., Monks, A., Sausville, E. A., Weinstein, J. N., Friend, S., Fornace, A. J., Jr., and Kohn, K. W. (1997) Characterization of the p53 tumor suppressor pathway in cell lines of the National Cancer Institute anticancer drug screen and correlations with the growth-inhibitory potency of 123 anticancer agents. *Cancer research* **57**, 4285-4300
40. Turenne, G. A., and Price, B. D. (2001) Glycogen synthase kinase3 beta phosphorylates serine 33 of p53 and activates p53's transcriptional activity. *BMC cell biology* **2**, 12
41. Martinico, S. C., Jezard, S., Sturt, N. J., Michils, G., Tejpar, S., Phillips, R. K., and Vassaux, G. (2006) Assessment of endostatin gene therapy for familial adenomatous polyposis-related desmoid tumors. *Cancer research* **66**, 8233-8240
42. Kandath, C., McLellan, M. D., Vandin, F., Ye, K., Niu, B., Lu, C., Xie, M., Zhang, Q., McMichael, J. F., Wyczalkowski, M. A., Leiserson, M. D. M., Miller, C. A., Welch, J. S., Walter, M. J., Wendl, M. C., Ley, T. J., Wilson, R. K., Raphael, B. J., and Ding, L. (2013) Mutational landscape and significance across 12 major cancer types. *Nature* **502**, 333-339
43. el-Deiry, W. S., Tokino, T., Velculescu, V. E., Levy, D. B., Parsons, R., Trent, J. M., Lin, D., Mercer, W. E., Kinzler, K. W., and Vogelstein, B. (1993) WAF1, a potential mediator of p53 tumor suppression. *Cell* **75**, 817-825
44. Nakano, K., and Vousden, K. H. (2001) PUMA, a novel proapoptotic gene, is induced by p53. *Mol Cell* **7**, 683-694

45. Sane, S., and Rezvani, K. (2017) Essential Roles of E3 Ubiquitin Ligases in p53 Regulation. *International journal of molecular sciences* **18**
46. Lu, X., Nannenga, B., and Donehower, L. A. (2005) PPM1D dephosphorylates Chk1 and p53 and abrogates cell cycle checkpoints. *Genes & development* **19**, 1162-1174
47. Shang, X., Vasudevan, S. A., Yu, Y., Ge, N., Ludwig, A. D., Wesson, C. L., Wang, K., Burlingame, S. M., Zhao, Y. J., Rao, P. H., Lu, X., Russell, H. V., Okcu, M. F., Hicks, M. J., Shohet, J. M., Donehower, L. A., Nuchtern, J. G., and Yang, J. (2010) Dual-specificity phosphatase 26 is a novel p53 phosphatase and inhibits p53 tumor suppressor functions in human neuroblastoma. *Oncogene* **29**, 4938-4946
48. Lu, Z., Wan, G., Guo, H., Zhang, X., and Lu, X. (2013) Protein phosphatase 1 inhibits p53 signaling by dephosphorylating and stabilizing Mdmx. *Cellular signalling* **25**, 796-804
49. Shaltiel, I. A., Aprelia, M., Saurin, A. T., Chowdhury, D., Kops, G. J., Voest, E. E., and Medema, R. H. (2014) Distinct phosphatases antagonize the p53 response in different phases of the cell cycle. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **111**, 7313-7318
50. Kitade, S., Onoyama, I., Kobayashi, H., Yagi, H., Yoshida, S., Kato, M., Tsunematsu, R., Asanoma, K., Sonoda, K., Wake, N., Hata, K., Nakayama, K. I., and Kato, K. (2016) FBXW7 is involved in the acquisition of the malignant phenotype in epithelial ovarian tumors. *Cancer science* **107**, 1399-1405
51. Mao, J. H., Perez-Losada, J., Wu, D., Delrosario, R., Tsunematsu, R., Nakayama, K. I., Brown, K., Bryson, S., and Balmain, A. (2004) Fbxw7/Cdc4 is a p53-dependent, haploinsufficient tumour suppressor gene. *Nature* **432**, 775-779
52. Takeishi, S., Matsumoto, A., Onoyama, I., Naka, K., Hirao, A., and Nakayama, K. I. (2013) Ablation of Fbxw7 eliminates leukemia-initiating cells by preventing quiescence. *Cancer cell* **23**, 347-361
53. Frescas, D., and Pagano, M. (2008) Deregulated proteolysis by the F-box proteins SKP2 and beta-TrCP: tipping the scales of cancer. *Nature reviews. Cancer* **8**, 438-449

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. Identification of p53 as a substrate of SCF(FBXW7).

A. Amino acid sequence of p53 with matching peptides by mass spectrometry marked in yellow. **B.** Cos7 cells were transiently transfected with pFlagCMV2-FBXW7 and whole cell extracts immunoprecipitated with anti-Flag monoclonal antibody or normal mouse serum (PI). Immunoprecipitates materials were analyzed by Western blotting. Lys: whole cell extracts from Cos7 transfected cells. **C.** The experiment was performed as in (B), but proteins were immunoprecipitated with anti-p53 monoclonal antibody or normal mouse serum. **D.** FBXW7 interacts with p53 in a yeast two-hybrid assay. L40 reporter strain was co-transformed with the indicated constructs. The interaction between the two-hybrid proteins is indicated by growth in the absence of histidine, DO-whl (dark red patch) and by the induction of *LacZ* expression (blue patches). Ras^{V12}/Raf interaction was used as a positive control. DB, fusion with the DNA-binding domain of LexA. AD, fusion with the activation domain of Gal4. **E.** *In vitro* ubiquitin ligation assay of ³⁵S labeled *in vitro*-transcribed/translated p53 was conducted in the presence or absence of the following products: cold *in vitro*-transcribed/translated FBXW7 or βTrCP, E1 (His₆-ubiquitin activating enzyme), E2 (His₆-UbcH3 and UbcH5a) and Ub (ubiquitin). Samples were incubated at 30°C for 1 hour. The bracket on the right side marks a ladder of bands corresponding to poly-ubiquitylated p53. **F.** The experiment was performed as in (E) except that the unlabeled F-box protein was substituted by a recombinant SCF(FBXW7) complex expressed in Sf21 insect cells. **G.** Cos7 cells were transfected with the indicated plasmids, and treated with MG132 for 4 hours before harvesting. Extracts were prepared as indicated in the Materials and Methods, and poly-ubiquitylated p53 visualized after Western blots of the Flag immunoprecipitations.

Figure 2. SCF(FBXW7) induces p53 degradation in normal growing cells.

A. Expression of p53 and cyclin E was studied in HCT116 and HCT116^{FBXW7^{-/-}} cells, and in HCT116 cells transfected with the indicated siRNAs. An immunoblot for α-Tubulin is shown as a loading control. **B.** U2OS cells were transfected with EGFP- or FBXW7-siRNA and, after 48 hours, cycloheximide (CHX) was added to the medium and cells were collected at the indicated times. Extracts were analyzed by Western blotting. p53 and cyclin E protein levels were quantified using ImageJ and normalized

to α -Tubulin level. Error bars represent the SD (n=3). *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01 using Student's *t* test. **C.** Cos7 cells were transfected with the indicated plasmids and, 18 hours later, extracts were subjected to Western blot. **D.** Serines and threonines of the putative CPDs of p53 protein are indicated in the upper panel. TD: transactivation domain. PRD: proline rich region. DBD: DNA binding domain. 4D: oligomerization domain. Neg: negative regulation domain. In the lower panel, the overexpression of FBXW7 on wild type or mutant p53 is shown. HEK293T cell were transfected with pFlagCMV2-p53 (wild type or mutant), and 18 hours later re-transfected with pCMVHA-FBXW7 or empty vector. Extracts were analyzed by Western blot. **E.** HCT116 and HCT116^{FBXW7-/-} cells were treated or not with Nutlin 3a for 24 hours, and extracts analyzed by immunoblot analysis. The quantitative fold change in p53 was determined relative to the loading control. **F.** Similarly to (D), HEK293T were transfected with pFlagCMV2-p53 or pFlagCMV2-p53 L14Q/F19G, and 18 hours later re-transfected with pCMVHA-FBXW7 or empty vector. Extracts were analyzed by Western blotting. The quantitative fold change in Flag-p53 or Flag-p53 L14Q/F19G was determined relative to the loading control.

Figure 3. FBXW7 is involved in the recovery of cell proliferation after DNA damage.

A. Cell proliferation assay of HCT116 and HCT116^{FBXW7-/-} cells after UV radiation. The amount of protein in extracts was taken as a measure of cell proliferation. Error bars represent the SD (n=4). *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 using Student's *t* test. **B.** Extracts were also used to analyze p53 expression by Western blotting. **C.** Quantification of protein levels shown in (B) using ImageJ and normalized to α -Tubulin level. Data are representative of three independent experiments. Error bars represent the SD. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 using Student's *t* test. U: non-irradiated cells. D: days after UV irradiation.

Figure 4. GSK3 phosphorylates p53 on Ser33 and promotes its ubiquitylation by SCF(FBXW7) and degradation.

A. *In vitro* kinase assay of cold *in vitro*-transcribed/translated HAp53 and a p53 mutant on Ser33 (HAp53 S33G) incubated with recombinant GSK3 β . Proteins were analyzed by Western blotting using an anti-phospho p53 (Ser33) antibody (left panel). In the right panel basal *in vitro*-transcribed/translated HAp53 phosphorylation was inhibited with

increasing amount of a specific GSK3 β inhibitor. **B.** Determination of phospho p53 (Ser33) status of wild type and *FBXW7*^{-/-} HCT116 and DLD1 cells. **C.** Analysis of phospho p53 (Ser33) status of DLD1^{*FBXW7*^{-/-}} cells treated or not with two GSK3 inhibitors (CHIR99021 and LiCl). **D.** DLD1^{*FBXW7*^{-/-}} cells were transfected with GSK3 α/β - or EGFP-siRNA, and 72 or 96 hours later, cell extracts were blotted with the indicated antibodies. **E.** DLD1^{*FBXW7*^{-/-}} cells were transfected with pCMVHA-FBXW7 or pCMVHA, and extracts analyzed by Western blotting. **F.** Expression of phospho p53 (Ser33) in DLD1 and DLD1^{*FBXW7*^{-/-}} cells after UV radiation. U: untreated cells. D: days after UV irradiation. **G.** Effect of LiCl on p53 S33 phosphorylation of DLD1^{*FBXW7*^{-/-}} cells after UV irradiation. Inhibitor was added 24 hours before harvesting. U: untreated cells. D: days after UV irradiation. The quantitative fold change in phospho p53 (Ser33) was determined relative to total p53 protein. Experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

Figure 5. The role of FBXW7 in the recovery of cell proliferation after DNA damage is mediated by the degradation of p53.

A. HCT116^{*FBXW7*^{-/-}} and HCT116^{*p53*^{-/-}} cells were transfected with the indicated plasmids, and 24 hours later irradiated (60 J/m²) or not. Crystal violet assay was performed from day 3 to day 7 post-UV. Images show data from day 5 after irradiation. Scale bars, 400 μ m. **B.** Quantification of crystal violet assay described in (A). Error bars represent the SD (n=3). The significance was obtained by comparing values of HCT116^{*p53*^{-/-}} pFlagCMV-p53 versus HCT116^{*p53*^{-/-}} pFlagCMV-p53 S33G cells using Student's *t* test: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001. Expression level of transfected plasmids is also shown.

Figure 6. Influence of FBXW7 on apoptosis induced by p53 after DNA damage and its role in the survival of breast cancer patients.

A. HCT116 and DLD1 wild type and *FBXW7*^{-/-} cells were irradiated and collected at the indicated times. Extracts were analyzed by Western blotting. U: untreated control cells. The quantitative fold change in cleaved PARP was determined relative to the loading control. Experiments were repeated three times with similar results. **B.** Kaplan-Meier analysis of wild type p53 breast cancer patients with wild type FBXW7 (n=1,453; orange line) compared with increased levels of FBXW7, FBXW7^{amp} (n=68; blue line).

Tick marks represent censored patients. The p values were obtained from the long-rank test of Mantel and Cox. **C.** Similar to (B) but comparing breast cancer patients with tumors $p53^{\text{loss}}/FBXW7^{\text{wt}}$ (n=852; orange line) versus $p53^{\text{loss}}/FBXW7^{\text{amp}}$ (n=73; blue line).

Figure 1

Figure 2

A

B

C

D

HEK293T

E

F

Figure 3

A

B

C

Figure 4

A

B

C

D

E

F

G

Figure 5

A

B

— HCT116^{p53-/-} pFlagCMV2 p53
 — HCT116^{p53-/-} pFlagCMV2 p53 S33G
 — HCT116^{FBXW7-/-} pFlagCMV2

Figure 6

A

B

C

